

Capacitive Discharge Ignition (CDI) System for Spark Ignition (SI) Engine (Pulse Control Circuit)

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A CDI module has "capacitor" storage of its own and sends a short high voltage (about over 300V) pulse through the coil. The coil now acts more like a transformer (instead of a storage inductor) and multiplies this voltage even higher. Modern CDI coils step up the voltage about 100:1. So, a typical CDI module output is stepped up to over 30kV output from the coil. The CDI output voltage of course can be higher. The huge advantage of CDI is the higher coil output and "hotter" spark. The spark duration is much shorter (about 300ms) and accurate. This is better at high RPM (revolution per minute) but can be a problem for both starting and/or lean mixture/high compression situations. CDI systems can and do use "low" resistance coils. To study the capacitive discharge ignition system, the circuit is divided into ten blocks. These are shown in Fig. 1.1 and the overview operations are as follows.

Figure1 Block Diagram of Capacitive Discharge Ignition System

ABSTRACT

Technology drive today many things has been replaced with better design and technique. The research throughout designing and constructing of Capacitive Discharge Ignition (CDI) system for Spark Ignition (SI) Engine which is based on electronic ignition and contact point ignition. CDI system is composed of pulse generation circuit, pulse control circuit, main charge and discharge capacitor coil and spark plug. Mainly composed of pulse control circuit and pulse generation circuit which main function is to generate DC high voltage when the DC 12V supply from car battery. Pulse control circuit generates the pulse to control (oscillator on and off state) and trigger gate drive pulse to the SCR. When the SCR from pulse control circuit open, the main capacitor discharge high voltage 300V from pulse generation to ignition coil. The coil generates high voltage 25-30kV which it depends on number of turn ration from coil primary and secondary winding. System is divided into ten blocks. The operation and function of each block is mentioned in detail. Design calculations for inverter, rectifier and selection of SCR, analyzing of components are highlighted for system.

KEYWORDS: Capacitive Discharge Ignition; monostable mode, Contact Point Ignition System, Electronic Ignition System

INTRODUCTION

Capacitive Discharge Ignition (CDI) is most widely used today an automotive and marine engines.

In figure1, pulse generation circuit is to generate the high voltage pulse using dc to ac voltage inverter, ac to dc voltage rectifier, and charge main capacitor. The pulse control circuit is to control the pulse generation circuit and trigger to the SCR using switching and trigger transistors. This system stores electrical energy of high voltage in a capacitor until the trigger releases the charge to the primary winding of a coil. In this system the coil is a pulse transformer instead of being an energy-storage device as is normal. To obtain a voltage of about 400V for the capacitor, the battery current is first delivered to an inverter (to change d.c to a.c) and then it is passed to a transformer to raise the voltage and to get dc voltage, full wave bridge rectifier is used. When the spark is required, the trigger releases the energy to the coil primary winding by 'firing' a thyristor (a type of transistor switch which, once triggered, continues to pass current through the switch even after the trigger current has ceased). Suddenly discharge of the high-voltage in excess of 30 kV in the secondary circuit to give a high-intensity, short-duration spark.

A. Capacitive Discharge Ignition (CDI) System

The system stores electrical energy of high voltage in a capacitor until the trigger releases the charge to the primary winding of a coil. In this system the coil is pulse transformer instead of being an energy-storage device as is normal. To obtain a voltage of about 400V for the capacitor the battery current is first delivered to an inverter (to change d.c to a.c) and then it is passed to a transformer to raise the voltage. When the spark is required the trigger releases the energy to

Figure3 Internal Block Diagram of 555 Timer

The 555 timer has two basic operational modes: one shot and astable. In the one-shot mode, the 555 is called a monostable multivibrator. The monostable circuit generates a single pulse of fixed time duration each time it receives an input trigger pulse. Thus it is named one-shot. If there is no triggering input, the circuit stays in its stable condition which is the off-state. The output stays at zero. Whenever it is triggered by an input pulse, the monostable switches to its temporary state. It remains in that state for a period of time determined by an RC network. It then returns to its stable state. In other words; a monostable multivibrator operates by charging a capacitor with a current set by an external resistance.

D. 555 Monostable Operation

In the Monostable Operation mode, the timer generates a fixed pulse whenever the trigger voltage falls below $V_{CC}/3$. When the trigger pulse voltage applied to the trigger pin falls below $V_{CC}/3$ while the timer output is low, the timer's internal flip-flop turns the discharging Tr . off and causes the timer output to become high by charging the external capacitor $C1$ and setting the flip-flop output at the same time. The voltage across the external capacitor $C1$, V_{C1} increases exponentially with the time constant $t=RA*C$ and reaches $2V_{CC}/3$ at $t=1.1RA*C1$

Figure4 Monostable Circuit using R and C

Hence, capacitor $C1$ is charged through resistor RA . The greater the time constant RAC , the longer it takes for the V_{C1} to reach $2V_{CC}/3$. In other words, the time constant RAC controls the output pulse width. When the applied voltage to the capacitor $C1$ reaches $2V_{CC}/3$, the comparator on the trigger terminal resets the flip-flop, turning the discharging Tr . on. At this time, $C1$ begins to discharge and the timer

output converts to low. In this way, the timer operating in the monostable repeats the above process. It must be noted that, for a normal operation, the trigger pulse voltage needs to maintain a minimum of $V_{CC}/3$ before the timer output turns low. That is, although the output remains unaffected even if a different trigger pulse is applied while the output is high, it may be effected and the waveform does not operate properly if the trigger pulse voltage at the end of the output pulse remains at below $V_{CC}/3$. Figure 4 shows such a timer output abnormality.

E. Design of Switching Circuit from Pulse Control Circuit

In proposed pulse control circuit, transistors perform as switching transistors. When the point from distributor open, transistor is turns on and triggered.

Figure 5 Operation Circuit for Q7

$I_1 = V_{BE}/R_{10} = 1.5\text{mA}$
 $-V_{in} + I_1R_9 + I_1R_{10} = 0$, the $V_{in} = I_1R_9 + I_1R_{10} = 1.41\text{V}$
 Assumed $I_C = 90\text{mA}$ (from C1815 = 2N2219A datasheet)
 For saturation,
 $R_C = (V_{CC} - V_{CE(sat)}) / I_{C(sat)} = 132\Omega$
 So, $R_C = R_{11} = 100\Omega$ is chosen.

For switching transistors,
 $I_B = 0.1I_C = 90\text{mA}$
 When Q7 is forward biased (get I_B current), turned on.
 And then, $V_{OUT} = V_{CC} - I_C R_C = 3\text{V}$
 So, $V_{OUT} = 3\text{V}$ triggered to M2.

From test condition, the trigger voltage from pin 2 is 3.6 V.

Figure6 Operation Circuit for Q8

For switching transistor Q8, when Q7 is turns on, Q8 turns off.

Therefore,

Assumed $I_C = 10\text{mA}$

$$R_C = (V_{CC} - V_{CE(sat)}) / I_C, (V_{CE(sat)} = 0.1\text{V}) = 1.19\text{k}\Omega$$

So, we choose $R_C = R_{16} = 1\text{k}\Omega$

For switching transistors,

$$I_B = 0.1I_C = 1\text{mA}$$

$$V_{R15} = V_{in} - V_{BE}, V_{in} = 10\text{V}$$

Therefore, charging voltage in C_7 is 10V.

For switching transistor Q6,

Figure7 Operation Circuit of Q6

When the output of M2 high, Q6 turns off.

Assume $V_{in} = 7.3\text{V}$

$$R_T = R_{20} + R_{19} = 4.4\text{k}\Omega$$

$$I_B = V_{in} / R_T = 1.65\text{mA}$$

$$I_B = 0.1I_C,$$

Therefore,

$$I_C = (1.65\text{m} / 0.1) = 20\mu\text{A}$$

$$V_{out} = V_{CC} - I_C R_C = 11.98\text{V} \approx 12\text{V}$$

This voltage applied to the pin 4 (reset) of the M1. So M1 is not active and can't give pulse to inverter circuit.

F. Design of Trigger Circuit

By comparison, 555 monostable from Pulse Control Circuit, $C_1 = C_{11} = 0.01\mu\text{F}$ and $R_A = R_{28} = 10\text{k}\Omega$. During this time, transistor Q9 is turned on and VR27 have zero voltage (R27 parallel with short line). So R27 can neglect.

Therefore, $R_A = R_{28}$

V_{C1} increase with time constant R_A . When the trigger pulse applied to the 2 pin falls below $V_{CC}/3$ while time output is low, the timer's internal flip-flop turns the discharging transistor off and causes the timer output to become high by charging the external capacitor C_{11} and setting the flip-flops output to become high by charging the external capacitor C_{11} .

Figure 8 Equivalent 555 Monostable Circuit Using R and C

Therefore, V_{C1} increases exponentially with the time constant t ,

Where $t = R_A \times C_1 \cdot \mu$

So, $= 10\text{k} \times 0.01\mu$
 $= 100\mu\text{s}$

During this time, Input voltage of pin 2, $V_2 < 4 (V_{CC}/3)$.

C_1 continues to charge until the voltage across it reaches $2/3V_{CC}$, at which point the output of 555 goes low and C_1 discharges through the resistor R_A to pin 7.

Therefore,

$$t_{\text{discharge}} = 1.1R_A \times C_1$$

$$= 110\mu\text{s}$$

During this time, charging of voltage in C_1 , $V_{C1} = 8\text{V} (2V_{CC}/3)$. The greater time constant t , the longer it takes for the V_{C1} to reach $2V_{CC}/3$. This means that charging time is longer in C_1 .

Figure9 Constructed CDI Circuit

Figure 10 Constructed of Pulse Control Circuit

Figure11 Trigger and output waveform of 555 M2

G. Conclusion and Discussion

Capacitive Discharge Ignition (CDI) system in this research is based on contact point and electronic ignition system. In contact point within the distributor system, rotation of the

shaft and breaker cam causes the distributor contact points to open and close. The contact point close and open once for each cylinder with every breaker cam rotation. Thus one high voltage surge is produced by the ignition coil for each cylinder every two crankshaft revolution.

SCR using in this project is high power and high current SCR, it has maximum 600V, 8A. Parallel capacitor commutation is used to turn off the SCR. It is protected with snubber circuit. In this research, the design and analyzing of pulse control circuit to generate high voltage in right time for engine have been described.

In other CDI system, switching and triggering circuit used MOSFET replacing switching transistors and 555 timer. In local market, switching transistors and 555 timers are easily to buy and low cost for construction. So, the proposed control circuit is designed switching transistors and 555 timers for triggering.

As a result, the proposed circuit is low cost, low emission and simple circuit to control the pulse for SCR and pulse generation circuit for spark ignition engine. It can be used not only spark ignition petrol engine but also spark ignition gas engine.

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